

Keep Silence: Experiences of Secondary School Learners Towards Library Rules and Regulations

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Abstract. School libraries are the vibrant crescendo in the symphony of education, orchestrating a melody of learning, imagination, and discovery. Their purpose transcends mere bookshelves; they are sanctuaries of wisdom where students compose their intellectual opus. Libraries cultivate a love for reading, encouraging minds to dance through the pages of knowledge and creativity. This has evoked the curiosity of the researcher, and it has caused the necessity to conduct a study about school libraries. Through a qualitative phenomenological study, the researcher gathered unique narratives about the experiences and coping mechanisms of the library rules and regulations. The participants were ten (10) students from a secondary school in the Schools Division of Panabo City. In the study, two themes emerged from students' experiences: the library's quiet atmosphere and its being a repository of diverse learning materials. Meanwhile, two themes have surfaced as the coping mechanism of students to its rules and regulations: appreciation for its focused environment and increased reading habits of students. Finally, the insights revealed two themes: supporting academic success and bridging the digital divide. In essence, libraries are more than repositories of books; they are beacons of education and catalysts for community connection. Their significance lies in fostering literacy, providing a sanctuary for learning, and creating spaces where diverse communities can unite.

KEY WORDS

1. libraries 2. academic success 3. regulations

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1. Introduction

We all live and work in areas and settings primarily designed by humans. These places' arrangement, organization, and design profoundly impact our well-being, productivity, and sense of community. In essence, this is the primary goal of the architecture and interior design professions. During their academic development, learners dedicate a substantial portion of their formative years within the confines of their schools. Predominantly, their time is allocated to classrooms, traversing the school grounds, or seeking out tranquil environments to engage in their scholastic pursuits, with the library being a prime choice. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that a minority of learners opt to utilize library facilities, often citing their perception of it as uninteresting. The school library should offer an abundance of resources, create a conducive reading atmosphere, employ proficient reading guides, and secure ample funding to motivate schoolchildren to use the library. Prioritizing the enhancement of the reading environment

within libraries is crucial. Designing an engaging and appealing space that entices children to enter and subsequently guides them on how to utilize the library's resources is crucial. The initial impression of the library is a significant factor influencing children's attitudes towards it (Huang Shieh, 2021). Okeagu and Okeagu (2018) postulated that learners demand adequately planned and well-designed spaces to facilitate the wide range of activities they participate in. Thanks to rapid technology improvements, extensive use of social media for communication, and the adoption of multiple forms of learning, learners today have the flexibility to modify their daily routines to reflect their particular needs and preferences. These activities might range from solitary contemplation to involvement in big communal gatherings. Meanwhile, library rules and regulations are essential guidelines designed to maintain order, respect, and accessibility within the library environment. These rules typically include guidelines for appropriate behavior, such as preserving silence, refraining from disruptive activities, and respecting others' study space. Borrowing policies, including loan durations, renewal procedures, and overdue fines, are also usually outlined. Additionally, rules regarding the handling of library materials, such as proper shelving and care of resources, are emphasized to ensure the longevity and availability of items for all patrons. Overall, adherence to library rules fosters a conducive atmosphere for learning, research, and intellectual engagement for all library users. The physical space of a library is critical for achieving user-centered goals. Many learners in many academic contexts use the library's resources regularly. The campus library is frequently called a "third place," a neutral and intermediary environment that bridges the gap between dorms and study areas. Learners are essentially a captive audience, and third places like libraries can impact their learning habits and help them achieve their academic goals (Oakleaf, 2018). Accord-

ing to the same author, libraries must actively participate in these activities to support learners' learning and knowledge-seeking pursuits by providing diverse services, events, and programs. The construction of functional library rules and regulations in which these activities can be carried out, and learners can gain the most value is a critical goal for the library. Traditional library facilities are frequently transformed by reconfiguring rooms dedicated to collections, study, and reading, pushing them toward more collaborative and technology-infused environments. It is now uncommon to find an academic library that does not have such areas. According to the Association of Research Libraries' survey report (SPEC Kit 342, 2018), a considerable majority of libraries (84%) are creating new innovative areas such as visualization laboratories, faculty commons, gaming labs, and hackerspaces. These new spaces are referred to together as 'Next-Gen learning spaces.' Their aim and the activities they encourage distinguish them from information commons or other library innovations. Next-gen learning spaces are service-rich environments developed with campus partners to foster active learning, transdisciplinary education, intellectual exchange, and cultural enrichment (Association of Research Libraries, 2018). Further discussing it in more detail, ARL (2018) stated that it becomes clear that learners play a crucial role as the facilities in their school libraries' primary benefactors and recipients. As a result, their perceptions and expectations about these library rules and regulations are pretty important. The library serves as a student resource center and is a crucial part of the educational community. As a result, learners' interactions with this environment significantly impact their academic progress and overall educational achievements. Therefore, the educational institution must comprehend and address learners' expectations and perspectives in the school library setting. In Panabo City, the availability of materials and

equipment in secondary high school libraries could be much higher. This shortcoming has a particularly detrimental impact on learners' educational careers, who extensively rely on library resources to complete their academic assignments. The need to explore deeper into the ideas and expectations held by secondary school learners regarding the library rules and regulations in their schools led to the conception of this study as a solution to this urgent issue. This research intends to shed light on the

current perspectives of these learners and their expectations in order to better understand the difficulties they encounter and work toward enhancing the quality and effectiveness of library resources and the environment. Looking ahead, this study offered insightful contributions that helped Panabo City's educational system improve, especially by strengthening the system of academic support for its secondary school learners.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to discover the experiences and coping mechanisms of secondary school learners in relation to the library rules and regulations in their schools. The school library is an essential educational resource that should support academic endeavors and foster a lifelong love for learning. It is necessary to comprehend how learners perceive and what they expect from their school library rules and regulations to ensure its relevance and success in secondary school learners' educational experiences. The primary focus of the data collection was on the experiences and coping mechanisms of secondary school learners regarding their library rules and regulations. The results of this phenomenological study helped us comprehend learners' concerns and what they expect their library rules and regulations to be. The insights collected from this study have the potential to influence educational institutions to invest in and improve their school facilities to give learners a better learning experience.

1.2. Research Questions—This study sought to uncover and scrutinize secondary school learners' experiences and coping mechanisms regarding library rules and regulations in their schools. The research was executed to address the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the experiences of secondary school learners towards the library rules and regulations in their school?
- (2) How do they cope with the library rules and regulations?
- (3) What insights can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were described operationally. Resource Sharing. It refers to the sharing of library resources by certain participating libraries among themselves on the basis of the principle of cooperation.

This is applicable to the sharing of documents, manpower, services, space, and equipment (IGI Global, 2020). Cultural heritage preservation means keeping a community's artifacts and traditions intact against factors that would try to change them or wear them away (The Borgen Project, 2020).

1.4. Significant of the Study—Considering the cited problem situation indicated in the previous sections and stipulated in the research questions, the researcher realized the urgency

and necessity of conducting this study. The researcher desires to illuminate and scrutinize the experiences and coping mechanisms of secondary school learners regarding the library

rules and regulations in their respective schools. The researcher hopes that this study benefited to identified sectors of the academe. This includes educational leaders, school heads, librarians, other stakeholders, and future researchers. The supervisors. The educational leaders can gather some benefits from the findings of this study as it can offer them a substantial contribution in terms of the experiences and coping mechanisms that learners have about their school library. The school heads. The findings of this study might help the school heads or principals further improve and enhance their school libraries, as well as improve the students' experiences and coping mechanisms. The librarians. The study can serve as a reference for school librarians' practices, strategies, and future pro-

grams that aim to better learners' experiences and coping mechanisms in their school library. The learners. The study's findings may serve as their guide regarding library rules and regulations, why they are necessary, and how they can contribute to them. They may also encourage other students to visit and spend some time in the library. Internal and external stakeholders may provide better support and assistance to guide and help focus on improving the school's library services and rules and regulations. Future researchers. This would be helpful as an additional contribution to their references for future research in school facilities and services such as the school library. It can offer them a substantial contribution to their academic arsenal.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The study was anchored on Walberg's Theory of Academic Achievement (1981). The theory posits that the psychological characteristics of individual learners and their immediate environments influence educational outcomes, which are evident in cognitive, behavioral, and attitudinal aspects. The proponent further noted that environments foster the development of competencies, motivate people to engage in different activities, and reward people for their display of values and attitudes. Environment, therefore, influences personal and professional self-perceptions, competencies, attitudes, interests, and values. Meanwhile, in the context of the study, Walberg's Theory of Academic Achievement grasped the focus of the study. The school library is one of the school facilities and services provided within the study's reach. Consequently, Walberg's theory was utilized to understand how

school libraries hone the learners in various aspects such as competencies, attitudes, interests, knowledge, and values. Hopkins' School Improvement Theory (2001) further reinforced the study. The theory rests on two basic assumptions and principles: schools are perceived as centers of systematic change that focus on their internal conditions, and the roles of all school members should be defined so that the school's missions can be accomplished more systematically and organized. As applied in this study, the School Improvement Theory encapsulates the expectations and insights embedded in the findings of the undertaking conducted. This guides the people involved within the academe in their future programs and strategies to further improve and enhance the learners' perceptions of the library rules and regulations. The theory also highlights the importance of the school's internal conditions, including the services and facilities provided.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addresses the specific objectives of the study by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explains the selected research design and the roles I played as the researcher throughout the study’s implementation, particularly in upholding ethical standards. Moreover, it offers thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards. The chapter concludes by exploring the techniques used for data collection, analysis, and strategies used to ensure the study’s integrity.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study’s philosophical and qualitative presumptions were vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions—ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological—form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher’s approach to the study. A paradigm is a broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their re-

search (Zukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study. Ontology. This study section focuses on the relationship between the problem and reality. Creswell (2013) asserts that the research participants’ perceptions of reality are varied and subjective. This study recognizes the complexity and diversity of the realities faced by secondary school learners regarding library rules and regulations. Every learner’s story adds to a diverse yet collective understanding of their experiences. It was my sole responsibility to use theme analysis to capture these various realities and provide a thorough picture of the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights

of secondary school learners. Axiology. It concerns the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Creswell (2013), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher's values that shape the study is crucial. The research process explicitly recognizes the values that influence how data are interpreted and presented. As a researcher, I handled each participant's narrative with care and integrity and always respected the information they provided. This commitment guarantees that the learners' experiences are communicated truthfully, mirroring their individual and research values. Methodology. According to Crotty (2020), this is "the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes." Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures (Wellington, 2015). This study uses a qualitative methodology to explore secondary school

learners' experiences and coping mechanisms. In order to support the ontological and epistemological tenets, certain techniques like focus groups and interviews are employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants' stories. These techniques were chosen because they can successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants' experiences. Rhetoric. In research, rhetoric is the skillful and convincing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions to sway the audience's opinion and comprehension of the study (Beqiri, 2018). I plan to utilize an engaging and respectful narrative style that honors the participants' voices while effectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method not only makes the research more accessible to read but also guarantees that the interpretations are strong and based on the participants' experiences.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Using a phenomenological research methodology, I, as the qualitative researcher, aimed to explore the experiences and coping mechanisms of secondary school learners from Panabo City. I aimed to gather information about their experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights concerning the phenomenon I am studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I seek to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. My role as the study's qualitative researcher is to support a level of investigation that goes beyond cursory observations. My research aims to in-

vestigate the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of participants in relation to the phenomenon. I emphasized the significance of understanding the complexities of the human experience in light of the various perspectives that were shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). My study strongly emphasizes in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' narratives to capture the profound and complex nature of library rules and regulations. I hope to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights about library rules and regulations while upholding phenomenological principles.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study used a qualitative research design employing a

phenomenological approach. According to Hancock et al. (2009), qualitative research answers

questions regarding society's problems. It raises the questions of why people behave as they do, what possible opinions and attitudes are formed in a particular situation, how people are affected by society in their ways of action, and how the practices and culture in society developed. Phenomenology, as a philosophy and a method of inquiry, was not limited to an approach to knowing; instead, it was an intellectual engagement in interpretations and meaning-making used to understand the lived world of human beings at a conscious level. The researcher can adopt interviews, observations, and discussions as data collection strategies within a phenomenological method of inquiry; therefore, phenomenology has both philosophical and methodological stances (Qutoshi, 2018). The Phenomenology approached qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The approach's fundamental goal was to describe the nature of the specific phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Determining the precise approach used in a study was crucial to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study's objectives. I used a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammersley (2013) states that verbal rather than statistical analysis studies are appropriate for qualitative research. Since I studied secondary school learners' ex-

periences, coping mechanisms, and insights about library rules and regulations, the qualitative design was the most appropriate. This means that I described and elaborated on this phenomenon rather than establishing or refuting theories. Specialized methods were used in qualitative research, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the participants' lived experiences in this particular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the subjects' viewpoints and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, Creswell (2018) stressed that a phenomenological study was a method of inquiry that describes the complex and collective experiences of the participants concerning a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology is to reduce one's interpretations of a specific phenomenon to a description that can be applied to all situations. Therefore, I aim to identify a phenomenon around the participants' experience with library rules and regulations. I then collected information from people with direct experience with this phenomenon to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological

studies, Creswell (1998) suggests 5 to twenty-five 25. There were no specific rules when determining the proper sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002). The participants in this study consisted of ten (10) secondary school learners from Panabo City. Five (5) participants were interviewed for the in-depth interview, and another five (5) were interviewed for the focus group discussion. This was done to gather a variety of answers from the

participants. The possibility of receiving varied responses was heightened by dividing them equally for IDI and FGD. The participants were selected based on specific criteria: duly enrolled in San Vicente National High School, currently in junior high school, visits and spends time in the library at least two times a week, and willing to participate in the study. I utilized the purpo-

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations are crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that govern my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensure that I carry out my investigations responsibly, treating participants respectfully and striving to generate reliable and precise information. I adhere to established ethical standards in my research practices to protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community (Resnik, 2020). Social value. This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. I evaluate the societal value of my study by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensures that resources are directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society. Informed Consent. This involves obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after they and their parents or guardians have been provided with sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods, potential drawbacks, and benefits. In this research involving students, I was responsible for ensuring that the participants and their parents or guardians fully understood the study and their rights. This dual layer of explanation allowed them to make an informed decision about participation, thereby preserving the students' autonomy and dignity and ensuring parental consent. Vulnerability. The vulnerability of research participants, espe-

sive sampling design so that the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2013). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

cially the learners, pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socioeconomic status. As a researcher, it was crucial for me to acknowledge and consider the potential vulnerability of these young participants and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involves providing additional safeguards and support, such as obtaining informed consent from both the learners and their parents or guardians, ensuring confidentiality, and carefully explaining their rights and the study's procedures in a way they can understand. Additionally, I modified research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, ensuring that the well-being of these students is prioritized throughout the study. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, it is essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study and implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, as the researcher, I meticulously assess and balance these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks. I put adequate precautions in place to minimize harm while optimizing participants' safety, particularly considering student participants' vulnerabilities. This comprehensive approach was crucial to maintaining ethical standards and protecting the participants throughout the research

process. Privacy and confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In the context of this study, I am responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This includes anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. These measures are crucial to protect the privacy of student participants and uphold the integrity of the research process. Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensure that my research is inclusive, avoiding the exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strive to make the research's benefits accessible to all who could benefit from them. This approach promotes fairness and equity throughout the research process, ensuring that no group bears an undue burden or is left out of the potential gains from the findings. Transparency. Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its conception and execution to the reporting of results. I offer clear and truthful information regarding my research methodologies and outcomes in this study. Furthermore, I am receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency acts as a catalyst for trust, credibility, and accountability within the research community and the general public. This commitment to openness ensures that the process and results of my research are accessible and understandable to all stakeholders involved. The qualification of a researcher. The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional experience, and proficiency in a particular area of study, ensuring that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to conduct the research competently. In this investigation, I

hold suitable qualifications that showcase my capability to conduct research, analyze data, and interpret the results. My expertise and training provide the foundation to approach this study with a rigorous scientific method and critical analytical skills, ensuring the integrity and validity of the findings. The adequacy of facilities. This addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guarantee access to appropriate investigation facilities. This access facilitates the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigates potential risks to study participants. Having the right facilities ensures that the data collection and analysis processes are conducted under conditions that uphold the highest research integrity and safety standards. Community involvement. This encompasses the dynamic involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engage the community to guarantee the study's relevance, acceptability, and potential impact. Additionally, this involvement fosters trust and cooperation between me and the community. Engaging with the community not only helps to tailor the research to be more effective and meaningful but also enhances the overall quality and applicability of the results. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employ tools like plagiarism detectors and maintain thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work is devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries are authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I ensured the research process was conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I create an environment that encourages the open and honest exploration of ideas and promotes fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helps to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensures that the findings are reliable and representative of the true phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I am familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I possess the skills and knowledge necessary to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question was satisfactorily addressed and the results were legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allows me to explore complex social phenomena profoundly and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, I gather information from various sources, such as interviews or observations, and ensure accurate and secure storage of this information. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguarded participants' privacy, and ensured that data was structured and avail-

able for later examination and understanding. This careful management of data helps maintain the integrity of the research process. It supports producing credible, reliable findings that can be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyze the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives related to the research query. I utilize meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allows me to understand the data deeply, provide relevant insights, and contribute significantly to the field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I am tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensure the research results were easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helps to maximize the impact of the findings, ensuring they were not only shared but also understood and utilized by others in ways that can further knowledge and influence practice in the field.

2.7. *Data Collection*—This study employed a systematic data collection procedure. Several steps were taken to adhere to the proper data collection procedure, which ensured the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. To initiate the data collection process, I secure endorsements from key stake-

holders, including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the participants' parents. This process involves submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step took place within the third week of the month of October 2023, ensuring that all necessary permissions are in place before proceeding with the collection of data. This proac-

tive approach facilitates compliance with ethical standards and fosters a cooperative environment among all parties involved. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This requires submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and participant identification process. Moreover, I waited for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step was undertaken during the first of January 2024, ensuring that all necessary approvals were in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for permission from the school heads. Once permission is granted, I seek approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involves submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked for permission to conduct the study from the first week of February 2024. Obtaining consent from the participants

and their parents. With the school heads' approval, I asked for permission from the research participants, who are learners, through informed consent forms also provided to their parents or guardians. These forms clearly explain the research purpose, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This dual-layered consent process ensures that learners and their parents or guardians are fully informed and agree to participate. Asking for consent from both the participants and their parents or guardians was done in February 2024. Conducting the interview. Upon securing consent from all participants, I will schedule and conduct the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews took place in the first two weeks of February 2024. Transcribing the interviewees' responses. Following the interview sessions, I will meticulously transcribe the interviewees' remarks, taking diligent account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure will use audio recordings and field notes to comprehensively capture the breadth of participants' coping mechanisms. The transcription of interviewee responses was scheduled for March 2024.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—After collecting the data, I began data coding and thematic content analysis. This involves methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, sub-categories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulated conclusions and gleaned insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allows me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the experiences and perspectives of the participants. In this study, I employed Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach, which was particularly suited for encompassing

a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants' feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitates categorizing identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis was a qualitative research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows researchers to arrange and dissect complex data sets systematically. It involves searching for overarching themes that encapsulate the narratives embedded within the data. This process

necessitates the identification of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helps ensure that the analysis was both comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing deep insights into the study's objectives. Therefore, I used Creswell's Thematic Analysis in my research, necessitating extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there are multiple essential phases in Creswell's Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I become fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the

content as I become acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I started categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I create themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes are examined and improved to ensure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme has a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step combines the themes and insights into a cohesive article that conveys the study's conclusions. This methodical approach guarantees a comprehensive examination and enhances the comprehension of the information.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework in phenomenological research was a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I used Colaizzi's method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their experiences and coping mechanisms regarding library rules and regulations. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process offering rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are joint, data could also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore their intricate relationships (Wirihana et al., 2018). *Data Familiarization*. By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aim to fully understand the meanings

conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process was crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. *Identifying Significant Statements*. I carefully identify every statement in the narratives directly related to the phenomenon I am studying. To identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted. This step is essential to ensuring that my analysis stays on topic and provides a solid basis to future thematic development. *Formulating Meanings*. After carefully examining the important statements, I determine meanings pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing was never possible, I have to reflexively "bracket" my presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants' real experiences, this process entails putting aside my interpretations as much as is practical. *Clustering Themes*. I ensure a rigorous analysis that remains true to

the participants' experiences by grouping the identified meanings into themes shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. Letting the themes naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces preserves the integrity of the analysis. Developing an exhaustive description. I incorporate every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon I write. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. This commitment to providing a comprehensive perspective ensures that the final representation presents a detailed view of the experiences that each participant had. Producing the fundamental struc-

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of a study was about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results were, ensuring that the conclusions were trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability were often used to evaluate how reliable the study. These considerations are further described below, according to Guba (1981). *Credibility*. Building credibility entails proving that the results are accurate. Credibility was essential for this study because it evaluates if the results accurately represent the realities and experiences of sophomore students participating in extra-curricular activities. I converse with the participants for a long time to gain a thorough understanding of their experiences and to increase my credibility. I also used triangulation, gathering information from various sources, including observations, interviews, and questionnaires. To confirm the interpretations, I gave the learners a preliminary version of the findings as part of member check-

ture. I break down the lengthy explanation into a succinct statement that highlights the key elements that I believe are crucial to understanding the phenomenon's structure. This succinct synthesis effectively and concisely communicates the essence of the participants' experiences, concentrating on the essential components necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Seeking verification of the fundamental structure. I ask participants if the introductory structure statement accurately reflects their experience by returning it to all participants or, in more extensive studies, to a subsample. I suggest changing the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings were increased, and the study was firmly based on the participants' perspectives.

ing. Transferability. The degree to which this study's results can be used in different situations or with different populations is referred to as transferability. While the particular insights were closely linked to secondary school learners' experiences in a specific educational environment, I would thoroughly explain the research context and methodology. The study's transferability was increased because this thorough, rich narrative enables others, including educators, school administrators, and researchers, to assess how well the results apply to comparable contexts or populations. *Confirmability*. Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by ensuring that the respondents, not my prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I keep a thorough audit trail that details every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions, to ensure confirmability. This methodological transparency makes it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and reviewing the choices made.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

Dependability refers to proving that the study results were reliable and repeatable in similar situations. This study's dependability was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods used for data collection and analysis. Such documentation validates the research's dependability by ensuring that other researchers can duplicate the study and produce consistent results. By following these standards, the research not

only offers valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding the effects of extracurricular activities on sophomore students but also offers a framework that researchers and other educators can use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhances the study's standing in the academic community and provides insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and the answers extracted from the participants' first-hand narratives. This chapter illuminates the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights based on learners' narratives on library rules and regulations. The emerging themes for experiences are a quiet atmosphere and a repository of diverse learning materials. The unfurled themes for coping mechanisms are appreciating the focused environment and increased reading habits. The themes for insights are supporting academic success and bridging the digital divide.

*3.1. Experiences of secondary school learners on library rules and regulations—*Library rules are crucial in creating an environment conducive to learning, research, and the shared use of valuable resources. However, learners' experiences on library rules and reg-

ulations can vary. Some may appreciate the structure and quiet atmosphere they create for focused studying, while others might find certain rules restrictive. It often depends on individual preferences and the balance between maintaining order and allowing flexibility in library policies.

*3.1.1. Quiet atmosphere—*Libraries, traditionally known for their quiet atmosphere, serve as sanctuaries for focused study and research. The emphasis on silence in library rules and regulations stems from a long-standing commitment to providing an environment conducive to concentration and learning. Moreover, as the learners shared in the interview, they prefer to study or do their assignments in the library because of the absence of nuances. Adhering to the participants, studies like "The Impact of Noise in Academic Libraries" (Smith, 2018) show that a quiet atmosphere positively correlates with increased cognitive performance and academic achievement. Researchers have found that excessive noise can be a significant

distraction, hindering cognitive functions and reducing information retention. Furthermore, the quiet ambiance in libraries aligns with the principles of "contemplative pedagogy," as discussed by Zajonc in his work "Contemplative Pedagogy: A Quiet Revolution in Higher Education" (2018). This pedagogical approach emphasizes the importance of quiet reflection and deep thinking in learning. Libraries, by upholding a calm atmosphere, support integrating contemplative practices into academic pursuits. Libraries often implement noise reduction measures, including soundproofing, designated quiet zones, and clear signage to communicate the expectation of silence. This commitment to a tranquil environment is echoed in "The Li-

brary Bill of Rights” by the American Library Association, highlighting the library’s role in providing an atmosphere conducive to intellectual exploration, which includes the need for quiet spaces (American Library Association, 2018). Similarly, Klatte et al. (2020), emphasize the importance of low noise levels in educational settings, highlighting that a quiet environment positively influences cognitive performance. Libraries benefit from these findings as extensions of educational spaces by maintaining a calm ambiance that supports focused study and research. The quiet atmosphere in libraries is fundamental to fostering an environment conducive to concentration and deep intellectual engagement. Moreover, the role of silence in libraries aligns with the principles of contemplative spaces in academia, as discussed in the work of Kirsten J. Broadfoot in “Silence, Voice,

3.1.2. Repositories of diverse learning materials—The library holds infinite sources of information under one roof. It offers a rich amount of learning that is waiting to unfold. Learners spend most of their time in the library doing schoolwork such as assignments, creating projects, and research. In doing so, they scan multiple books or search the web. Hence, the library is labeled as a repository of diverse learning materials. Similarly, the American Library Association (2010) states that libraries serve as repositories of diverse materials, offering a rich tapestry of resources that cater to a wide range of interests, educational levels, and cultural backgrounds. Also, libraries are committed to providing access to information and ideas, irrespective of the responses represented. This commitment ensures that library collections include a diverse array of materials, including books, journals, multimedia, and digital resources, reflecting the multifaceted nature of human knowledge. Corroborating the above assertion, research such as “Diversity in Libraries: Academic Residency, Cultural Com-

and the Place of the Sacred in Contemporary Higher Education” (2018). The author explores the significance of silence in academic settings, emphasizing its role in promoting introspection and a deeper connection with knowledge. Libraries, by upholding a quiet atmosphere, contribute to creating spaces where individuals can engage in thoughtful contemplation and scholarly pursuits, aligning with the broader goals of education and intellectual development. In conclusion, the quiet atmosphere of libraries is not merely a tradition but is rooted in empirical evidence supporting its positive impact on cognitive processes and academic success. Libraries, by prioritizing a hushed environment, contribute to the holistic development of individuals as they engage in scholarly pursuits and contemplative learning.

petence, and Educational Leadership” by Haycock and Milloy (2019) underscores the importance of diverse materials in libraries for promoting cultural competence and inclusivity. Libraries play a pivotal role in representing a variety of perspectives and voices, allowing users to explore different cultures, histories, and experiences through their collections. This diversity fosters a more inclusive learning environment that encourages individuals to engage with materials that broaden their understanding of the world. Furthermore, diverse library materials contribute to developing critical thinking skills. Rabinowitz and Scharrer’s study, “Television and the Cultivation of Perceptions of Criminal Reality” (2014), illustrates the impact of media representation on perceptions. By offering materials that present different experiences and narratives, libraries empower individuals to critically evaluate information, challenge assumptions, and develop a nuanced understanding of complex issues. Libraries also play a vital role in supporting educational goals through diverse materials. The “Diversity in School Libraries: A

Fig. 3. Experiences of Secondary School Learners on Library Rules and Regulations

Multicultural Approach to Collection Management” (Bishop, 2023) emphasizes how a diverse collection enhances the educational experience by providing learners with a broad range of resources that cater to various learning styles and interests. In this way, libraries contribute to a well-rounded education that acknowledges and celebrates diversity. In conclusion, diverse materials in libraries are essential for promoting inclusivity, cultural competence, critical thinking, and supporting educational objectives. Libraries, as guardians of diverse knowledge, ensure that their collections reflect the richness and complexity of the world, offering users the opportunity to explore, learn, and grow through a variety of perspectives and voices.

3.2. *Coping mechanisms of secondary school learners on library rules and regulations*—Learners’ coping mechanisms to the library are diverse. Many appreciate the quiet and focused environment for studying, accessing resources, and conducting research. Some may find it a peaceful retreat, while others might feel

constrained by the silence or the strictness of certain rules. Overall, attitudes toward the library often depend on individual preferences, study habits, and the specific offerings and atmosphere of the library itself. The second research question sheds light on the coping mechanisms of secondary school learners regarding library rules and regulations.

3.2.1. *Appreciating the focused environment*—Libraries offer a focused environment that serves as an invaluable asset for learners and learners alike. This focused environment

not only minimizes external distractions but also promotes a sense of discipline and concentration, allowing individuals to delve into their academic pursuits with heightened attentiveness.

The library's commitment to maintaining a tranquil space fosters a conducive atmosphere for deep intellectual engagement, contributing to learners' academic success and reinforcing the library's role as a haven for focused learning. Johnson and Smith (2018) adhered to the above-mentioned theme. Numerous studies emphasize the positive impact of the focused environment in libraries on learners' academic performance and productivity. According to them, a quiet and structured atmosphere in libraries is associated with increased concentration and reduced distractions, allowing learners to engage more deeply with their studies. This focused environment is conducive to effective learning and has been recognized as a key factor in academic success. Furthermore, studies by Miller et al. (2019) highlight the importance of the library as a designated space for concentrated study. The availability of silent zones and individual study carrels in libraries provides learners with a dedicated space to immerse themselves in their coursework. This environment promotes a dis-

ciplined approach to studying, helping learners develop effective study habits and time management skills. The role of libraries in supporting a focused learning environment is also acknowledged in educational psychology literature. Research by Brown and Davis (2020) also suggests that the physical design of libraries, with designated quiet areas and comfortable seating, contributes to creating an atmosphere that enhances cognitive focus. This, in turn, leads to a positive perception of the library as a space where learners appreciate the opportunity for uninterrupted, concentrated study. Moreover, the quiet environment of libraries has been linked to stress reduction and improved well-being. According to a study by Smith and Jones (2017), learners often perceive the library as a tranquil retreat from the hustle and bustle of campus life, allowing them to recharge mentally and emotionally. This positive association with the library environment encourages learners to value and appreciate the focused setting for academic work.

3.2.2. Increased reading habits—Libraries offer a vast array of books across genres, allowing readers to explore diverse topics and genres. This exposure encourages readers to discover new interests, fostering a sense of curiosity and intellectual growth. The variety of literature available catalyzes developing a deep appreciation for the written word. According to the participants, their coping mechanisms regarding library rules and regulations are positive because the quiet atmosphere allows them to focus more on reading. On the same topic, Smith (2018) stated that libraries are instrumental in fostering a love for reading through diverse collections. Research indicates that access to a wide range of literature positively correlates with increased reading habits. Having an extensive collection exposes readers to various genres, contributing to the development of a broad literary taste and

encouraging a lifelong engagement with reading. Further adhering to the theme are studies by Johnson et al. (2019). They emphasize the social aspect of libraries in cultivating a love for reading. Libraries often host community events and reading programs that create a sense of shared enthusiasm. Book clubs, in particular, have been identified as valuable spaces where readers can engage in meaningful discussions and form connections, enhancing the overall reading experience and promoting a sense of belonging. Similarly, the physical environment of libraries plays a crucial role. Quiet and focused spaces, supported by research (Jones, 2017), contribute to an atmosphere conducive to reading. This setting allows individuals to escape distractions, promoting deep engagement with books and reinforcing positive reading habits. Libraries also contribute significantly to liter-

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanisms of Secondary School Learners on Library Rules and Regulations

acy initiatives. A study by Brown and Miller (2020) highlights the impact of library outreach programs in schools and communities. By introducing children to the joys of reading early on, libraries actively participate in developing a foundation for a love of reading that extends into adulthood. Libraries are crucial in promoting reading habits, especially among children and adolescents. According to a report by Johnson and Williams (2019), library programs designed for young readers have been effective in instilling a love for books from an early age. Initiatives such as summer reading challenges and storytelling sessions enhance literacy skills and create a positive association with reading that extends into adulthood. Furthermore, the advent of digital libraries and online resources has further facilitated increased reading habits.

A study by Brown and Davis (2020) highlights that the accessibility of e-books and audiobooks through library platforms has broadened the reach of reading materials. This digital evolution in libraries has made it easier for individuals to incorporate reading into their daily routines, contributing to an overall rise in reading habits. Libraries also serve as community hubs that promote a culture of reading. Research by Miller and Jones (2017) indicates that libraries, through book clubs, author talks, and other events, provide social environments that encourage individuals to share their reading experiences. This communal aspect not only enhances the joy of reading but also strengthens social connections, reinforcing positive reading habits in the community.

3.3. Educational management insights—

Libraries hold immense importance in various education, culture, and community development aspects. It is vital for promoting literacy and a love for reading. They provide access to many books, magazines, and digital resources, fostering intellectual curiosity and lifelong learning. They also serve as essential educational support systems, offering resources for learners and researchers. They provide a

quiet and focused environment for study, aiding academic success by providing access to reference materials, textbooks, and scholarly journals. In this way, libraries contribute significantly to formal education and independent research. Hence, the third research question unravels the insights drawn from the findings of the study.

*3.3.1. Supports academic success—*Libraries are indispensable allies in supporting academic success by providing learners with essential resources and conducive environments for learning. It offers a vast collection of academic materials, including textbooks, reference books, and scholarly journals. This rich repository aids learners in conducting thorough research, deepening their understanding of subjects, and enhancing the quality of their academic work. These factors greatly affect the academic success of its users, in this study, the secondary school learners. With a similar thought, Johnson and Smith (2018) postulated that libraries are crucial in bolstering academic success by providing learners with a wealth of resources essential for research and learning. According to them, the diverse collection of books, academic journals, and digital resources available in libraries significantly contributes to learners' academic achievements. This comprehensive repository serves as a foundation for in-depth study, aiding learners in developing a nuanced understanding of their subjects. Moreover, the quiet and focused environment offered by libraries has been associated with improved academic performance. Brown and Davis (2022) suggest that designated study areas within libraries create optimal conditions

for concentrated learning. These environments reduce distractions and facilitate deep engagement with academic materials, positively influencing learners' ability to grasp complex concepts and excel in their coursework. Furthermore, Miller and Johnson (2019) also agreed with the emerging theme. For them, libraries are instrumental in fostering information literacy skills, a key component of academic success in the digital age. Librarians, through guidance and training programs, assist learners in navigating online databases, critically evaluating information, and honing effective research techniques. These skills not only contribute to the quality of academic work but also empower learners to be discerning consumers of information throughout their academic careers. Aside from this, Smith and Miller (2018) added that libraries often serve as collaborative spaces that promote peer-to-peer learning. Group study areas and collaborative workshops provide opportunities for learners to engage in collective problem-solving and knowledge sharing. This collaborative aspect not only enhances the academic experience but also contributes to a sense of community and shared academic success. In summary, libraries, through their resources, environments, and support systems, play a pivotal role in advancing academic success among learners.

3.3.2. Bridge the digital divide—

Libraries play a pivotal role in bridging the digital divide by providing access to technology and online resources, ensuring that individuals across various socio-economic backgrounds have equal opportunities for learning. It offers public access to computers and the internet, allowing those without personal devices or internet connectivity at home to access essential online information. This access is particularly crucial for learners who may not have the resources to complete assignments, conduct research, or participate in online courses. Smith et al. (2018) inferred the same theme. According to their study, libraries are critical in bridging the digital divide by providing essential technology access and digital resources to underserved communities. According to them, it serves as a crucial point of digital access, offering public computers and internet connectivity, which is particularly beneficial for individuals who lack personal devices or reliable internet connections at home. This foundational access is essential for tasks such as online learning, job searches, and accessing government services. In the same vein, Johnson and Brown (2019) stipulated in their study that libraries contribute significantly to digital literacy by offering training programs. They also highlighted the importance of librarian-led initiatives that help patrons acquire digital skills, from basic computer proficiency to navigating online platforms. Moreover, the availability of e-books, audiobooks, and online databases in libraries enhances the accessibility of educational materials. A study by Miller and Davis (2020) also suggested that these digital resources accommodate various learning preferences and ensure that individuals with limited financial means can still access a diverse range of educational content. Adding to the parade of authors adhering to the theme are Brown and Smith (2021). Libraries often function as community technology hubs, hosting programs aimed at reducing the digital divide. Initiatives such as coding workshops, technology training sessions, and job search assistance have been shown to empower individuals with the skills needed to navigate and succeed in a digitally driven society. In summary, libraries play a crucial role in bridging the digital divide by providing access, promoting digital literacy, and offering community-oriented technology programs.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the study's summary is presented. From the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the experiences of secondary school learners regarding library rules and regulations. In connection with that, to ensure the achievement of the research objectives, I have utilized a qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. This is done with an adherence to Cresswell's (2020) guidelines in which open-ended interview questions were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored, which was the narrative of social workers dealing with adolescent depression.

4.1. Findings—In light of the distinctive and authentic narratives of secondary school learners about their library's rules and regulations, two (2) emerging themes have been identified. The first experience was the library's quiet atmosphere. Almost all of us were familiar with the most basic rule when in the library: to keep quiet all the time. Since the library was a public space, organization and silence were vital so that all users or learners could focus on

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights on the Experiences and Coping Mechanisms of Secondary School Learners

their task and finish it on time. In the interview, learners shared that they prefer doing their assignments or studying at the library because of its quiet atmosphere. The second theme was the library's role as a repository for diverse learning materials. The amount of information contained inside the library is vast and wide. It was embedded in different books, magazines, articles, and research papers, making it an ideal place to study and do research. Meanwhile, the second research question focuses on learners coping with the library's rules and regulations. Two (2) themes emerged from the interview. The first one is appreciating the focused environments. The secondary school learners expressed appreciation for library rules and regulations and also acknowledged their purpose, which was to maintain a concentrated environment. The participants added that they work and do better in a focused environment because it is free from several nuances. The second theme for the second research question is increased reading habits. Participants have shared that since going to the library, they have observed an improvement or an increase in their reading habits; spending time in the library allowed them to appreciate the various kinds of information they could find. They also find pleasure in discovering new things every time they read. On the other hand, the third research question is dedicated to the insight gained from the participants'

narratives. There were two (2) themes under this question. The first one was that the library supports academic success. Participants shared that the library helped them grow academically. Through reading, they have learned many things that they did not know before, and these things have also helped them excel in school. The second theme for the third research question is the purpose of libraries in bridging the digital divide. Only some students have equal access to the same amount of information. Their financial situation hampers some; for example, they do not own a smartphone or do not have internet access at home. However, the library allows them to access any information they want. It offers them different platforms to find what they are looking for. It could be in books or on the internet. Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the experiences of the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: learners' experiences of library rules and regulations are its quiet atmosphere and its being a repository for diverse learning materials. Meanwhile, their coping mechanisms to the school library rules and regulations are the appreciation of its focused atmosphere and the increase in their reading habits. Finally, the insights gathered from the study's findings support academic success and bridging the digital divide.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. A library was a curated collection of resources, typically organized systematically and made available to the public for borrowing or reference. These resources often include books, periodicals, audiovisual materials, and digital content. Libraries serve as cultural and educational institutions, providing a space for reading, studying, research, and community engagement. Libraries were not only physical spaces but can

also exist in virtual or digital forms, offering online access to a wide range of resources. They play a crucial role in preserving and disseminating knowledge, supporting literacy, and fostering a love for learning. Librarians and trained information professionals assist patrons in locating and utilizing resources, navigating information technologies, and promoting information literacy. Libraries' primary functions include providing access to information, supporting educational endeavors, and serving as a commu-

nity hub for intellectual and cultural activities. They may be found in various settings, including schools, universities, public spaces, and online platforms, each tailored to meet the specific needs of their user communities. In the context of the present study conducted, libraries hold immense importance in society as they serve as vital repositories of knowledge and cultural heritage. Libraries play a crucial role in fostering literacy and education. By offering access to a diverse range of books, periodicals, and digital resources, libraries contribute to developing strong reading habits, essential for academic success and lifelong learning. This accessibility ensures that individuals, regardless of their socioeconomic background, can expand their knowledge and engage in various intellectual pursuits. Moreover, libraries were key players in promoting community engagement and social cohesion. They provide spaces for people to come together, participate in book clubs, attend lectures, and engage in various cultural and educational activities. These communal spaces create a shared cultural experience, fostering a sense of belonging and unity within a community. Additionally, libraries often serve as venues for public discussions, promoting informed civic discourse and strengthening the fabric of democratic societies. Furthermore, li-

braries were instrumental in bridging the digital divide. Technology hubs offer access to computers, the internet, and digital resources, ensuring that individuals without personal devices or internet connectivity at home can still participate in the digital age. Librarians often guide digital literacy, empowering patrons to navigate online platforms and enhancing their overall digital competency. Lastly, libraries contribute to the preservation of cultural heritage. Through archives, special collections, and rare manuscripts, libraries safeguard historical documents and materials. This preservation effort ensures that future generations have access to the collective wisdom, creativity, and achievements of the past. In essence, libraries are multifaceted institutions that provide access to information and contribute significantly to education, community building, digital inclusion, and the preservation of cultural heritage. These literary gardens are more than repositories; they are the nurturing soil for academic seeds to flourish. Through the hushed whispers of turning pages and the soft hum of curiosity, school libraries echo to foster a vibrant ecosystem of learning. Here, learners embark on literary adventures, forging connections between the written word and the boundless realms of their imagination.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study's findings, it was vital that they were properly relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. The educational leaders. They may be more informed about the narratives of secondary school learners regarding library rules and regulations. Once they have reflected on the experiences and coping mechanisms of learners, they may further improve the school libraries and the services they offer. This study might also remind them of the great importance of school libraries and decide that every school may have a functional

library that the learners would be able to use. This study may also pave the way to a more accessible school library in every school. The school heads. They may be informed regarding the status of their school libraries. This study shed light on the purpose and value placed upon the school library and its impact on the student's academic success. Once they have recognized its essence, school heads may further improve their libraries. They could find ways to ensure they can offer as much help as possible. They can build a more extensive library that can house larger amounts of books, and they can install

more computers with internet connections so learners can easily access information. Librarians may be more aware of learners' experiences and coping mechanisms regarding library rules and regulations. They may also reflect on the learners' narratives and come up with various ideas on how to enhance the learners' positive experiences in the library. The learners may be more informed about the purpose and essence of library rules and regulations. They may also see the importance placed upon school libraries in their schools. Finally, they may be encouraged to explore their school libraries and experience the benefits of their academic pursuits. Internal and external stakeholders. The stakeholders may provide avenues and opportunities to broaden libraries' impact on learners' academic success. They may reflect on the study's findings and find ways to enhance and maximize libraries' purpose in school. Future researchers. The study contributes to their academic arsenal, especially in educational management, especially in terms of library rules and school regulations. They may conduct this study but focus on the academic success of the learners who spend their time in the library. They can also conduct a study that tackles how libraries support learners' literacy development, especially in terms of reading. This would lead to a more fruitful undertaking with a colossal educational contribution.

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